

Oxo-Molybdenum(V) Complexes. Part II. Molybdenum(V) Complexes with Hydroxamic acids

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Manuscript received 10 November 1972; accepted 15 September 1973

A number of Oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes of hydroxamic acids of the type, $[\text{MoO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH}_2)]$ (where RH_2 = a molecule of hydroxamic acid) have been synthesised and characterised.

These complexes are coloured, crystalline, stable and diamagnetic. Since the difference in elemental analysis between Mo(V) and Mo(VI) are slight, the diffuse reflectance spectra, IR spectra, decomposition temperatures were determined for characterising Mo(V) complexes.

SEVERAL types of Oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes with 1,10-phenanthroline¹, nitrile¹, 2,2'-dipyridyl², 2,2'-dipyridyl-1,1-dioxide³, thiourea⁴, substituted 1,10-phenanthroline⁵, pyridine⁶ and quinoline carboxylic acids⁷, N-benzoylphenyl hydroxylamine or substituted hydroxylamine⁸ etc. have been described in the literature. Hydroxamic acids with RCONHOH grouping (where R = alkyl or aryl radical) have been used widely as spectrophotometric reagent⁹ and extracting reagent¹⁰. In recent years, attempt has been made to isolate stable, crystalline complexes with hydroxamic acids¹¹⁻¹⁴, but complexes of oxo-molybdenum(V) have not yet been described. The encouraging and extensive studies on oxo-metalcation, dioxo-molybdenum(VI)¹⁴ in our laboratory have also inspired to initiate a similar effort on oxo-molybdenum(V). The aromatic hydroxamic acids studied: benzohydroxamic acid (BH_2); *o*- and *p*-chloro BH_2 ; cyclohexane hydroxamic acid (CH_2); *p*-anisyl (*p*- AH_2) and quinoline 8-hydroxamic acids ($\text{Q}'\text{H}_2$). In general, it was observed that in aqueous solution oxo-pentachloro molybdate ion (MoOCl_5^{2-}) reacts with any of those aqueous solution of hydroxamic acids in CO_2 atmosphere to provide green and orange crystalline compounds. The pH of the solution was found to be around 2.0-3.0. The insoluble product was identified to be oxo-hydroxy-bis(hydroxamato)molybdenum(V).

The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents and so reflectance spectra were recorded (Fig. 1). The spectral bands for the complexes are not well defined. From Fig. 1, the only band assignments which can be made reasonably are for the (440-460) nm band for oxo-hydroxy-bis(cyclohexane hydroxamato) molybdenum(V) and all other complexes exhibit a second band within (600-680) nm excepting cyclohexane derivative. All the complexes show a third band within (750-900) nm (Table I). The approximate peak positions for the above complexes are given purely on the visual observation.

The bands are so broad that no correct assignment can be made without further analysis. Molybdenum (VI) complexes, on the other hand with no *d*-electrons available provide only charge-transfer band

All the complexes described here, are diamagnetic in nature. This diamagnetism may be due to polymerisation of the complexes with the consequent interaction of electron spins on the neighbouring Mo atoms which removes paramagnetism. Unfortunately, molecular weight determinations which support the above conclusion are unsuccessful due to the insolubility of complexes in solvents suitable for cryoscopic measurements.

All the complexes exhibit strong, sharp absorption bands in the IR around 980-990 cm^{-1} , typical of a metal = oxygen double bond¹⁵. Any oxy-metal cation involving a double oxygen absorbs at a lower frequency¹⁶. The frequencies, however, may vary widely as the bond order changes¹⁵. Besides, showing strong absorption band around 980-990 cm^{-1} , complexes show a broad band around 3450-3600 cm^{-1} . This is due to OH absorption band¹⁷. The relative lowering of 73 cm^{-1} , 27 cm^{-1} and 23 cm^{-1} of carbonyl absorption in the benzo-, cyclohexane and *o*-chloro benzohydroxamic acid complexes with respect to free reagents and relative increase of 40 cm^{-1} , 46 cm^{-1} and 10 cm^{-1} of C-N absorption indicate that co-ordination of hydroxamic acid is through carbonyl oxygen (Table 2).

The attempt was also made to isolate oxo-alkoxy-bis(hydroxamato) molybdenum(V) by refluxing oxo-hydroxy-bis(hydroxamato) molybdenum(V) with anhydrous ethanol but failed. This was due to quick oxidation of Mo(V) to Mo(VI).

Attempts to determine oxidation states of molybdenum in all these complexes did not quite materialise. However, the nature of the visible spectral and IR bands in all these complexes have little doubt

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1. Oxo-hydroxo-bis(*p*-chlorobenzohydroxamato)molybdenum(V) (--- · · · · ·)
2. Oxo-hydroxo-bis(*p*-anisylhydroxamato)molybdenum(V) (-----)
3. Oxo-hydroxo-bis(quinoline 8-hydroxamato)molybdenum(V) (—————)
4. Oxo-hydroxo-bis(*o*-chlorobenzohydroxamato)molybdenum(V) (-0-0-0-0-0-0-)
5. Oxo-hydroxo-bis(benzohydroxamato)molybdenum(V) (-Δ-Δ-Δ-Δ-Δ-)
6. Oxo-hydroxo-bis(cyclohexanehydroxamato)molybdenum(V) (- · · · · ·)

TABLE 1. REFLECTANCE SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	1st band (nm)	2nd band (nm)	3rd band (nm)
[MoO(OH)(BH) ₂]	—	600—620	776—850
[MoO(OH)(<i>p</i> -chloroBH) ₂]	—	650—670	720—770
[MoO(OH)(<i>o</i> -chloroBH) ₂]	—	620—640	850—900
[MoO(OH)(<i>p</i> -AH) ₂]	—	—	750
[MoO(OH)(QH hydrox) ₂]	—	660—680	775—800
[MoO(OH)(CH) ₂]	440—460	—	750

about quinquevalency of molybdenum. The difference in decomposition point in these complexes in comparison with the corresponding bis(hydroxamato)-

dioxo molybdenum(VI) complexes reported in the literature¹⁴ is a further support of quinquevalency of molybdenum in all these complexes (Table 3).

Experimental

The following hydroxamic acids were used to prepare compounds of Mo(V) :

(a) Benzo-; (b) *p*-anisyl-; (c) *o*-chloro-; (d) *p*-chloro-; (e) cyclohexane-hydroxamic acid; (f) quinoline 8-hydroxamic acid. The cyclohexane hydroxamic acid was prepared according to Chatterjee¹⁸. The synthesis of quinoline 8-hydroxamic acids will be reported in a separate communication. Others were prepared following standard procedures^{13,19}. Ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate was prepared according to Palmer²⁰.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis(hydroxamato) molybdenum(V) : An aqueous solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloro-

TABLE 2. IR SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Mo = O stretch (cm ⁻¹)	C-N stretch (cm ⁻¹)		C = O stretch (cm ⁻¹)		O-H stretch (cm ⁻¹)
		Complex	Reagent	Complex	Reagent	
1. [MoO(OH)(BH) ₂]	990	1360	1320	1587	1660	3448
2. [MoO(OH)(CH) ₂]	980	1379	1333	1613	1640	3570
3. [MoO(OH)(<i>o</i> -chloroBH) ₂]	990	1365	1355	1587	1610	3570, 3448

TABLE 3. ANALYSIS, COLOUR, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES AND DECOMPOSITION POINTS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis		Mag. susceptibilities	Decomposition temperature (°C)*
		% Mo	% N		
[MoO(OH)(BH) ₂]	Green	F : 24.2 R : 24.0	6.85 7.0	Diamagnetic	115(189-90)
[MoO(OH)(o-chloroBH) ₂]	Green	F : 20.35 R : 20.30	5.8 5.9	Diamagnetic	195(187-88)
[MoO(OH)(p-chloroBH) ₂]	Green	F : 20.40 R : 20.30	5.8 5.9	Diamagnetic	165-80(187-88)
[MoO(OH)(p-AH) ₂]	Green	F : 20.9 R : 20.8	6.1 6.0	Diamagnetic	140-70(190-92)
[MoO(OH)(QH hydrox) ₂]	Green	F : 23.0 R : 22.8	6.0 6.08	Diamagnetic	Not determined.
[MoO(OH)(CH) ₂]	Orange	F : 23.0	6.9	Diamagnetic	125-40(208-10)

* Decomposition temperature in parenthesis are for corresponding Mo(VI) complexes precipitated from aqueous medium (Ref. 14). Other figures stand for Mo(V) complexes.

molybdate (1 mole) and aqueous solution of either free hydroxamic acids or its sodium salt (3.0 moles), previously deaerated by passing CO₂ were mixed when an orange-red colour was developed. Through this solution, CO₂ was passed at least for 30 min. when complexes of characteristic colour began to separate. It was then filtered, washed several times with deaerated water and finally dried over CaCl₂.

All the complexes prepared were deep green to light green except oxo-hydroxo-bis (cyclohexane-hydroxamato) molybdenum(V) which was orange.

The analysis, colour, magnetic susceptibilities and decomposition points are given in Table 3.

Molybdenum content in the complex was estimated by decomposition with conc. H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and then precipitated as MoO₂(oxine)₃. Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro combustion technique and magnetic susceptibility was determined by Guoy method where CuSO₄ · 5H₂O was used as calibrant.

The reflectance spectra were obtained on a Zeiss PMQ II spectrophotometer with RA3 reflectance attachment, using magnesium oxide as a reference standard. The IR spectra were scanned on a Parkin Elmer Spectrophotometer using KBr disc technique.

Acknowledgement

Grateful thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta (Burdwan University), to Dr. S. L. Gupta (Burdwan Raj College), to Prof. D. P. Graddon and Dr. G. M. Mockler of New South Wales University (Australia) for reflectance spectra, to Dr. A. Syamal for IR spectra and to Dr. R. L. Dutta for constant encouragement and IR spectra.

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